

Super Mario Bros.: Three Decades Since His First Adventure

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Good day to all readers of CoolJapan.es. It is an honour for me to bring you what will be my first article —not news— dedicated to the world of video games, my greatest passion. It is precisely in the land of kitsune and samurai that video games managed to emerge from the crisis they faced during the 1980s. And all of this thanks to a single company, a handful of people, and one character.

We cannot talk about video games without mentioning the incomparable Super Mario, the amiable character created over thirty years ago by Shigeru Miyamoto for Nintendo, better known to children in the 1980s than Mickey Mouse himself. Coming from the world of comics and illustration, his creator faced a few rocky projects at the start of his career as a designer. Nevertheless, he never wavered in his determination to take Nintendo to the position it has reached over the past thirty years. Much of this success is due to our moustachioed hero: Mario.

Hiroshi Yamauchi, president of Nintendo at the time Miyamoto began his journey with the company, tasked him with an adaptation of the video game *Radar Scope*, which had been a commercial failure outside Japan —although it enjoyed moderate popularity within its borders—. The company trusted its employees and tried again until achieving resounding success. In this article, I will take a look at the most important titles of history's most international Italian plumber —and his brother Luigi—.

With the collaboration of engineer Gunpei Yokoi, another key figure at Nintendo, Miyamoto redesigned the game to make the most of its programming and to require less investment from the company than creating an entirely new game from scratch. This is how *Donkey Kong* and Jumpman, Mario's original name, came to be. It was the first time at Nintendo that they created the story first and then adapted the gameplay to fit it, while also ensuring that the imposed mechanics were not altered.

Radar Scope – left – and Donkey Kong – right –

Mario —that is, Jumpman— was born in 1981, already designed as the hero who had to rescue the damsel in distress in this video game, saving her from the King Kong parody represented by Donkey. He already had many of the visual characteristics of the Mario we all know: his moustache, cap, and overalls... Although it is worth noting that he began his adventures as a carpenter.

In the second Donkey Kong game, *Donkey Kong Jr.*, Jumpman returned but as Donkey and his son's adversary —the only time Mario has ever been an enemy in a video game—. Donkey's son had to rescue his father from the cage in which Mario had imprisoned him. In *Donkey Kong 3* —from 1983—, Jumpman was replaced by Stanley, who faced Donkey and a swarm of fearsome bees using his insecticide. Mario and Donkey would meet again in 2004 on the Game Boy Advance with *Mario vs. Donkey Kong*, a game in which puzzles would take centre stage, more than the platforming itself. Finally, they would face off again in *Mario vs. Donkey Kong: March of the Minis* —released in 2006 for the Nintendo DS—.

Returning to the 1980s, it was also in 1983 that Miyamoto joined Satoshi Tajiri —the future creator of Pokémon— to develop the arcade-style game *Mario Bros.* This was the first adventure where Mario received the name we know today, and where his brother Luigi also appeared as we know him, thanks to the game's multiplayer nature.

However, Miyamoto and Takashi Tezuka —director and designer, and game designer, respectively— wanted to replicate this success with a much bigger adventure, where Mario would face a true odyssey: an entire world to explore and an army of enemies to overcome. Mario was now a plumber, also known as Super Mario, using pipes to discover secret passages and whole levels to advance on his journey to rescue the Princess of the Mushroom Kingdom —later named Peach— from the clutches of his arch-nemesis Bowser, the evil king of the Koopas —a species in the Mario games resembling real-world turtles, but somewhat humanised—. Each level had to be completed within a set time limit to finish the adventure.

Numerous secrets, objects that granted astonishing powers such as temporary invulnerability, growing in size, or throwing fireballs, and alternative paths to progress, including routes above the clouds, made *Super Mario Bros.* —1985— the first true, fully-fledged Mario video game. It was a smashing commercial success —only later surpassed by *Wii Sports*, nearly thirty years later, another Nintendo title—. The game itself, along with its unforgettable musical themes by the great composer Kōji Kondō, became a part of global popular culture.

Super Mario Bros., released in 1985 for the Family Computer (Famicom) in Japan and for the Nintendo Entertainment System (NES) in Western markets

Super Mario Bros. was not a video game confined to a static screen, nor one in which the entire image had to change to reveal more of the stage, as continued to happen in many later titles. As the player moved forward, the phenomenon of side-scrolling occurred —a technique previously used in *Excitebike*, another game developed under Miyamoto’s direction— allowing for far greater dynamism in the adventure.

Mario and Luigi also appeared in *Wrecking Crew*, a game centred on demolishing buildings and battling enemies, this time equipped with hammers. Players could even create their own levels to test themselves.

Later, a direct sequel was developed exclusively in Japan. However, it was poorly received in the West even before release, due to the extreme difficulty of the levels shown to Nintendo of America and because it was considered overly similar to its predecessor. This game would later be known as *Super Mario Bros.: The Lost Levels* and was eventually released years later on the Super Nintendo as part of the 1992 compilation *Super Mario All-Stars*.

Thus, a game created by Miyamoto's team for Fuji TV —*Yume Kōjō: Doki Doki Panic*— was adapted by replacing its main characters with those from *Super Mario Bros.*, while modifying only the introduction and ending—even the soundtrack remained unchanged. It was released in Europe in 1989 and later arrived in Japan in 1992 as a new version of *Doki Doki Panic*.

From this title came several enemies that would later become staples of the Mario franchise, such as Shy Guys and Birdo.

Shy Guy and Birdo, original characters from *Doki Doki Panic*, later incorporated into the Mario franchise

This instalment was followed by *Super Mario Bros. 3*—alongside *Super Mario 64* and *Super Mario World*, widely regarded as some of the finest Mario games— released in Japan in 1988.

Tezuka and Miyamoto once again joined forces on a title that already included someone who would later become a key figure at Nintendo: executive producer Satoru Iwata. Its graphics pushed the NES to its limits; in fact, the game cartridge enhanced performance thanks to an additional chip with expanded RAM capabilities. The game featured memorable music, exceptionally well-designed levels, and new items that would become part of the franchise's legacy.

Mario and Luigi travelled across seven different worlds, rescuing seven kings from the clutches of King Koopa's children—each distinct and named in tribute to one of the game's programmers— before ultimately confronting Bowser himself and once again saving Peach.

Left: *Super Mario Bros. 3* title screen. Right: gameplay screen featuring Mario in one of the game's levels.

It was Yokoi who, in addition to designing Nintendo's first handheld console —the legendary Game Boy, if we do not forget the also previously designed by Yokoi, Mr. Game & Watch systems— delivered one of the finest titles in its catalogue in 1989: *Super Mario Land*. One of the most innovative entries in the series, it even introduced vehicles, such as a submarine.

It was not Yokoi's only Mario project. In 1990, *Dr. Mario* was released, a puzzle game sharing similarities with *Tetris* and *Columns* —the latter originally developed for PC in 1989, but propelled to worldwide fame by SEGA. Moreover, in 1991 Gunpei Yokoi released what would become the final Game & Watch title, *Mario the Juggler*.

In 1992, he also oversaw *Super Mario Land 2*, in which Mario faced a new villain: Wario, who would go on to become a recurring character in the series and eventually star in his own games, beginning with *Wario Land: Super Mario Land 3* for the Game Boy in 1994 —a true classic.

With the arrival of the SNES —the Super Nintendo Entertainment System— Nintendo released *Super Mario World* in 1991, still regarded today as the most complete two-dimensional Mario game ever created. It introduced Yoshi the dinosaur as Mario's companion and mount, featured an expansive overworld map, and showcased masterful level design, particularly in its abundance of items and secret routes.

Soon after, Nintendo launched what would become one of the most celebrated Mario-related sub-series: *Mario Kart*.

Its first instalment revolutionised racing games, as success was not determined by pure speed, memorising every track, or adhering to the serious simulation style typical of other driving titles. In *Mario Kart*, what truly matters is mastering your character and deploying items found along the track in ways guaranteed to provoke your rivals —usually in direct proportion to how often you send them crashing into a shell or slipping on a banana peel. Winning is important, certainly, but it is not the ultimate goal; the real objective is sheer, uncontrollable laughter.

Combined with the light-hearted nature of the Mario cast, the result was a transformation of the racing genre at the time.

Super Mario Kart (1992, SNES) and *Mario Kart 8* (2014, Wii U; 2017, Nintendo Switch –Deluxe version–)

By the original publication date of this article —2015— the *Mario Kart* series had seen eight official instalments, the most recent being *Mario Kart 8* for the Wii U, along with three additional spin-offs. Over time, the games have improved graphically, introduced new tracks and characters, reintroduced classic circuits from earlier entries as homage, and added new items with which to disrupt opponents and gain an advantage. In the most recent titles, players can even glide or briefly take to the air.

The original game made use of the so-called “Mode 7”, a technique that created a sense of three-dimensionality by rotating and scaling a texture to alter its perspective, thereby giving depth to the plane while the gameplay itself remained two-dimensional. This technique was also used in titles such as *Tales of Phantasia* (by Namco) and *F-Zero*, another title from Nintendo which predated *Mario Kart* and vice versa. Although it was not the first driving game to feature Mario — that distinction belongs to *Famicom Grand Prix: F-1 Race* (1987) — it was the first entirely devoted to the universe of our moustachioed hero and his characters.

Here is the mechanical monstrosity known as the Virtual Boy

In 1995, players were treated to several Mario titles with the launch of Gunpei Yokoi’s Virtual Boy —an early 3D headset, although not true virtual reality, as the images did not change according to the user’s movements— capable of displaying stereoscopic 3D images. Although the console was a commercial failure due to its high price and uncomfortable design —the combination of black and intense red visuals hardly encouraged extended play sessions— its twenty-two-game catalogue included some noteworthy titles. Among them was *Mario’s Tennis*, the first true tennis game starring Mario —unless one counts the plumber’s uncanny resemblance to the chair umpire in *Tennis* (NES, 1984), also developed by Nintendo.

This would not be the only sporting appearance of Mario and his friends. Later titles included solid entries such as *Mario Superstar Baseball* and the thoroughly enjoyable *Super Mario Smash Football*, both released for the Nintendo Gamecube in 2005.

Mario would eventually appear alongside his friends and even with Sega's Sonic the Hedgehog in sports games dedicated to the Olympic Games; the first of these appeared in 2007 to coincide with the Beijing Olympics, and also had a portable edition for the Nintendo DS. Another interesting Mario title for this console was *Mario Clash*: essentially a full remake of the original *Mario Bros.*, but adding the possibility for players to use pipes to move forward or backward through the stage across multiple depth layers, thanks to the stereoscopic 3D mechanic.

However, the game that gained the most importance was *Super Mario World 2: Yoshi's Island*. As its name suggests, in this title Yoshi and his dinosaur friends took centre stage, becoming the playable character for the entire adventure, since Mario appears as a baby in this instalment —though he still manages to wear his iconic cap.

What stands out most about this game, apart from its gameplay mechanics —Yoshi throws eggs, performs jumps Mario cannot, transforms into vehicles, etc. — is its graphical level. Using the Super FX 2 chip, this game features larger and higher-quality sprites than before, screen transitions, zooms, new graphical effects, and a much more striking watercolour and cartoon-like look compared to previous *Super Mario Bros.* entries.

In 1995, *Yoshi's Island* arrived on the Super Nintendo, featuring Yoshi and Baby Mario

This game had a sequel in 2006 for the Nintendo DS. Among its gameplay innovations, it included a huge variety of different enemies to face using Yoshi's mechanics, such as throwing eggs, gliding through the air, and more. It also stood out for its improved graphics, taking advantage of the superior power of the Nintendo DS compared to the SNES.

Later, in 2014, another installment was released for the Nintendo 3DS, called *Yoshi's New Island*, which was chronologically set between the two previous titles. With Tezuka as the only member of the original production team involved in this release, it did not reach the same level of quality as its predecessors, though it still maintained a good standard —it repeated too many situations and even reused previous soundtracks— while taking advantage of the 3DS's superior capabilities and stereoscopic 3D features.

The last major Mario game for the Super Nintendo was *Super Mario RPG: Legend of the Seven Stars*, an adventure co-produced with Squaresoft —the company behind, among others, the *Final Fantasy* series— that presented a Mario game like never before. It offered a fun story, turn-based combat, and a soundtrack featuring, among others, Kōji Kondō and Nobuo Uematsu, the latter being the star composer of *Final Fantasy* and one of the most respected music composers in video game history.

Because it appeared during the final years of the Super Nintendo console, it did not receive the recognition it deserved in the West. However, the studio Alphascream, partly formed with former Squaresoft staff, later developed several spiritual sequels to this game. All shared a very family-friendly tone, suitable for all ages, light-hearted humour, and a manga-inspired visual style leaning towards European and American comic/cartoon aesthetics. The first sequel was *Mario & Luigi: Superstar Saga* –2003– for the Game Boy Advance, in which players control Mario and his brother Luigi throughout the game world and in turn-based battles.

It was followed by *Mario & Luigi: Partners in Time* –2005– for the Nintendo DS, in which players also control baby versions of Mario and Luigi. After that came the amusing *Bowser's Inside Story* –2009–, a game in which the protagonists' stages take place inside Bowser himself, their arch-enemy —as the title indicates— who occasionally becomes a battle companion. Each installment in the Mario & Luigi series offers a tremendously fun adventure.

Mario and Luigi facing Bowser and Baby Bowser with the help of Baby Mario and Baby Luigi in *Partners in Time*, which was released in 2005 for the Nintendo DS

Mario & Luigi: Dream Team was the first installment of the *Mario & Luigi* series for Nintendo 3DS, and it saw the light of day in 2013. In it, our charismatic hero had to face both the game's real-world environment, in three dimensions—his world—and Luigi's dream world, presented in two dimensions—also taking advantage of stereoscopic 3D. The next title in this series would appear in 2016 as a crossover with the *Paper Mario* series, from Intelligent Systems—the creators behind the *Fire Emblem* series—titled *Mario & Luigi: Paper Jam*.

Going back to 1996, and with the Nintendo 64 in hand, *Super Mario 64* hit the market, considered by many as the best Mario game and one of the greatest video games in history—for some users, **the** greatest video game of all time. If Miyamoto had revolutionized gameplay with the early *Super Mario* titles or his first *The Legend of Zelda* (1986, for Nintendo Entertainment System) in two dimensions, it was with this game that he truly set a new standard.

A three-dimensional environment—polygonal, not stereoscopic, mind you—free camera movement, a wide range of possible actions in levels, and well-designed stages, together with its replayability—the game encourages players to revisit areas to fully complete them and extract 100% of the experience—can only be praised. The capabilities of this game would be copied, paid homage to, and emulated even in other Nintendo titles—features such as a free camera in a video game are now almost mandatory in platformers or adventure games.

Super Mario 64 game screen

The title enjoyed a truly remarkable re-release on the Nintendo DS —*Super Mario 64 DS*, launched in 2004—, which added the possibility of playing as additional characters—including a tutorial level with Yoshi—, multiplayer mode, and mini-games taking advantage of the console’s second, touch-sensitive screen. It was somewhat awkward to play, though, as the device lacked a second analogue stick, making camera control a real hassle. Nevertheless, it was an excellent conversion and a way to enjoy a video game masterpiece in portable format.

In 1999, *Mario Party* was released, a collection of mini-games in which each player controlled a character from the Mario series. It combined board-game-style boards with these mini-games and was designed primarily for social play, which earned it enormous success and led to the development of up to nine sequels—the last at the time of this article’s original publication in 2015, *Mario Party 10* for Wii U— spanning all Nintendo consoles available since then.

The Game Boy Color was not left without its own Mario title, even if it was a re-release of an existing game, the original *Super Mario Bros.* for NES. In 1999, Nintendo delivered a portable, full-colour Mario just like the original console version, additionally including the new levels from *Super Mario Bros.: The Lost Levels*, allowing the use of the Game Boy Printer, and featuring a world map similar to *Mario Land 2* or *Super Mario World*.

Also in 1999, Nintendo surprised players with a new IP from HAL Laboratory, where Satoru Iwata was president and Masahiro Sakurai—creator of *Kirby* and long-time lead of the *Smash* series— had a major role: *Nintendo All-Star! Dairantō Smash Brothers*, better known outside Japan as *Super Smash Bros.* As its title suggests, it was a Nintendo game where the company’s greatest stars came together to brawl mercilessly. Characters from the Mario series appeared, along with Link, Samus, Kirby, and some Pokémon, all from other Nintendo franchises.

This game, once again, set a precedent both within and outside the company. Today, similar productions include *DreamMix TV World Fighters* for Playstation 2 and Nintendo Gamecube, released in 2003, and the more recent *Playstation All-Stars Battle Royale* for Playstation 3 and Playstation Vita, released in 2012. The gameplay mechanics and controls are unlike typical fighting games such as *Street Fighter* or *Fatal Fury*, which are more robust, tactical, and deliberate —though not slow—, and where combos require complex button sequences or perfect timing of movements.

Learning to play *Super Smash Bros.* is very straightforward, which explains its enormous success and popularity across all kinds of audiences, not just fans of fighting games —exactly the goal Miyamoto had when hiring HAL— although mastering the game is highly challenging and, above all, demands countless hours mastering all the characters and facing them in battle.

From left to right, and top to bottom: Fox, Luigi, Samus, and Mario in *Super Smash Bros*

Each character is truly unique, and the way they play attests to this. Adding to this the varied origins of each character and the result of mixing their worlds, the outcome is this fun and chaotic video game. With the first installment being a success, more followed soon after: the next was in 2001, *Super Smash Bros. Melee* for the Nintendo Gamecube, considered by many fans as the best iteration of the series. Then, in 2008, came *Super Smash Bros. Brawl* for the Nintendo Wii, developed by Sakurai's new studio, Sora Ltd.; a game that could be played with the iconic Wii Remote but also with the Gamecube controller —something that has been preserved in the latest entries. The most recent game —as of the original publication of this article— is *Super Smash Bros. for Wii U* and *Super Smash Bros. for 3DS*, released in 2014 as two independent but connected editions. A distinctive feature of this entry is the use of stereoscopic 3D on the Nintendo 3DS and the Gamepad on Wii U.

Throughout the Smash series, characters from different Nintendo franchises, as well as from second-party —dependent or related companies, or Nintendo subsidiaries— and third-party —independent companies that have developed games for Nintendo—, were gradually added. This made it possible, for example, to see Sonic, Snake from Metal Gear, or Mega Man from Capcom facing off against the rest of the Nintendo characters.

Returning to role-playing games, Intelligent Systems released in 2000 the first of another subseries: Paper Mario. As its name suggests, in this game the world of Mario and its characters appear as if made of paper. The series constantly plays with both two and three dimensions, a feature that would be greatly expanded in its later iteration for the Nintendo 3DS. Subsequent games in this family appeared on the Nintendo Gamecube —*Paper Mario: The Thousand-Year Door*, 2004—, on the Nintendo Wii —*Super Paper Mario*, 2007—, and finally on the Nintendo 3DS —*Paper Mario: Sticker Star*, 2012.

Screenshot of *Super Paper Mario*, released in 2007 for the Nintendo Wii

Mario and the other characters acquire strange abilities always related to this two- and three-dimensional game, such as turning into a paper airplane, a paper boat, or folding at will. The Paper Mario series, while closely linked to the Mario & Luigi role-playing series, is considered a set of episodes not directly connected to each other, although the new title I mentioned earlier brings both together in a single game—a level of integration that had previously only occurred in very basic ways. For example, *The Thousand-Year Door* is closely related to *Super Mario RPG* on a narrative level. The Wii entry, initially planned for Gamecube, was more carefully designed as a platform game than an RPG—although it still retained that mode—and was the one to most fully incorporate three-dimensional environments.

In 2002, under the direction of Yoshiaki Koizumi, Nintendo surprised us with a new mainstream Mario release, that is, one linked to the main *Super Mario Bros.* series: *Super Mario Sunshine*. By equipping Mario with a device capable of shooting water jets at will, the F.L.U.D.D. gave players many enjoyable moments, new ways to solve levels, and new abilities for the character, such as floating in the air, running faster, or jumping higher thanks to the water jets. Mario is on holiday on a paradisiacal island with his friends when he suddenly finds himself in jail because an evil version of him has been vandalising the island. He is allowed to go free in exchange for cleaning all of Isle Delfino, which provides the excuse to introduce the new gameplay mechanics. It did not represent a revolution, but it did inspire other developers and games with its water- and paint-based mechanics —such as Warren Spector’s *Epic Mickey*.

In 2006, after Miyamoto and his team decided to return to two dimensions and create platform and adventure games in the purest style of the classic *Super Mario Bros.* —with side-scrolling— *New Super Mario Bros.* emerged: a game that not only revived this concept but also brought back enemies and situations from the older Mario games.

It was another major addition to the Nintendo DS catalogue, offering a new Mario game while adhering to the classic premises of the series and introducing the Mega Mushroom, which allowed Mario and Luigi to smash through the environment as they moved.

Mario destroying part of a level, an effect the player can experience in *New Super Mario Bros.*

It was no coincidence that this title became the best-selling game on that console, and Nintendo would delight fans with new entries in the future. For example, the Wii version, released in 2009, included a cooperative mode well-suited to the style of that console, allowing several players to share the same experience. In this case, it was also the best-selling game on the console, excluding *Wii Sports*. It would be followed by *New Super Mario Bros. 2* in 2012, and *New Super Mario Bros. U*, also in 2012. In *New Super Mario Bros. 2*, issues such as Mario's excessive obsession with collecting coins, the cooperative mode being limited to two players, and the soundtrack being reused from the previous Wii entry stood out, although it ended up being a solid Mario game.

The Wii U edition was developed concurrently and released alongside the console itself. Players could use the Wii U Gamepad, the Wii Remote, or the Wii U Pro Controller — essentially the new version of the classic Gamecube controller for games that did not handle the current Nintendo machine controls well and aimed to resemble the control style of, for example, the Nintendo Gamecube or Super Nintendo. This game allowed up to five players to play together simultaneously and, via Nintendo's Miiverse service, to post images, share opinions about levels, or give tips on completing them. Additionally, players could import their own Mii —customisable Nintendo console avatars— into the game for participation in certain modes.

A special edition was released in 2013 to celebrate the thirtieth anniversary of Luigi's appearance —*New Super Luigi U*, also for Wii U— featuring new levels and excluding Mario entirely from the game.

It was with *Super Mario Galaxy*, for Nintendo Wii and released in 2007, that Nintendo Tokyo EAD, under the direction of Yoshiaki Koizumi, once again crafted a masterpiece. Considered the game with the most positive reviews in history, it offered a Mario adventure while adding new twists to gameplay. In this case, the focus was on gravity and its changes, and how they directly affected Mario. Levels were spread across galaxies, each with small planets where our protagonist faced different gravities, enemies, and a variety of unique situations.

Official artwork of *Super Mario Galaxy*

It also includes random events in the form of comets, which force Mario to complete a level within a set time or with minimal health —meaning a single hit causes the player to fail—, or face a double, whom he must overtake to complete the level. It was the first Mario game in which a second player could join on-screen simultaneously with the first to solve the game together —cooperative mode— if we don't take *Mario Bros.* into account. Its soundtrack was directed by Mahito Yokota, who, after several trials that didn't quite fit, decided the music should be orchestrated rather than using the usual MIDI format. The celebrated Kōji Kondō contributed some tracks to provide stylistic variety.

A direct sequel followed three years later, in 2010: *Super Mario Galaxy 2*. Initially planned as a revised version of the first *Galaxy*, development ultimately expanded to implement more new features rather than relying so heavily on the original. In this second, also outstanding installment, Mario can once again ride Yoshi through levels, and the player encounters more varied challenges than in the first *Super Mario Galaxy*.

It also allows free travel between levels via Mario's starship, which even houses characters related to the plumber. The game features dynamic level design: stages can be altered according to the rhythm of the music, causing blocks to appear or disappear, or changing the direction of gravitational fields.

For the Nintendo 3DS, *Super Mario 3D Land* was developed in 2011. It was the first Mario game for this console, taking advantage of stereoscopic 3D to give new meaning to its gameplay, while simultaneously using two-dimensional plane design and polygonal depth. It masterfully combines the classic *Super Mario Bros.* style —side-scrolling, 2D perspective— with the modern approach to three-dimensional exploration and camera work found in contemporary games. Nintendo aimed to create a game that would appeal both to enthusiasts of the classic Mario titles and to younger audiences familiar only with 3D entries. It was the first Mario game to sell over five million units on 3DS.

Mario wearing his tanuki —Japanese raccoon dog— outfit in *Super Mario 3D Land*

Two years later, in 2013, Nintendo released a sequel to this game, called *Super Mario 3D World*, this time for the Wii U. Whereas the previous title had paid homage to *Super Mario Land*, this one honoured *Super Mario World*. The game brought back the countdown system for completing levels and the flagpole at the end of each stage—elements already present in the original *Super Mario Bros.* from 1985. The game areas were open for free exploration, and players could choose which level to play from those available, exploring and uncovering new secrets.

The latest *Super Mario Bros.* title released during the writing of this article was *Super Mario Maker* for the Nintendo Wii U, in 2015. Originally conceived as a tool for Nintendo’s level design team, they suggested to Takashi Tezuka that it could be launched as a game for the public, and he agreed, seeing it as a way to encourage players’ imagination and creativity.

Thanks to the plumber’s thirtieth anniversary, the game offers almost endless possibilities: players can create and test their own levels, or download levels made by others, vote on them, comment on them, and more.

The editor is controlled via the stylus and the Wii U Gamepad, allowing players to do all kinds of outrageous things in a level—including having enemies appear from the blocks where Mario normally gets items, to catch the player by surprise. To add variety and also evoke nostalgia, the game lets players choose between different visual styles: the classic *Super Mario Bros.*, *Super Mario Bros. 3*, *Super Mario World*, and finally *New Super Mario Bros.*

Official box art for the Japanese and European original versions of *Super Mario Bros.* from 1985

That’s all for this article. I’ve skipped over quite a few related games—either because they weren’t really important or didn’t belong to the main sagas. Anyway, thanks for reading my work, and see you next time!

Sources

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